

FRIEDRICH–ALEXANDER–UNIVERSITÄT ERLANGEN–NÜRNBERG

**RESEARCH PROJECT ON THE STRUCTURE OF
LIPID NANO PARTICLES USING SMALL ANGLE
NEUTRON AND X-RAY SCATTERING**

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Motivation

Lipid nanoparticles (LNPs) are complex, multicomponent, and polydisperse systems whose mesoscopic structure plays a decisive role in drug delivery. The aim of this research project was therefore to obtain a deeper understanding of the internal structure of LNPs. Specifically LNPs that are compositionally and structurally close to those used as carriers in the BioNTech/Pfizer mRNA vaccine were investigated. In particular, the focus was on their mesoscopic architecture and size distribution. For this purpose, the scientific methods of PCS and SAXS/SANS were applied. As a starting point, the model proposed by Unruh et al. was adopted.

According to this model the Comirnaty[®] vaccine is composed of five major components: mRNA, ALC-0315, ALC-0159, DSPC, and cholesterol, all dispersed in an aqueous solvent such as D₂O. In the present study, however, the two ALC lipids were replaced: ALC-0315 was substituted by glyceryl trioctanoate, and ALC-0159 was replaced by DMG-PEG2000. These substitutions allowed the formation of new LNP systems that were subsequently investigated.

Two motivations underpinned this approach. First, ALC-0315 is extremely expensive, and it is therefore of interest to test whether a cheaper substitute could be used to design viable vaccine carriers. Second, it was particularly interesting to investigate whether glyceryl trioctanoate can form nanoparticles of similarly small size and architecture as the well-established LNPs formulated with ALC-0315, since such small particles had not been observed with glyceryl trioctanoate before.

1 Materials and Methods

The following description is primarily based on the work of Unruh [9], with further details and orientations taken from the Masters thesis of Gallo [2]. In the experiments, drug-free lipid nanoparticles were prepared according to the composition of the commercial Comirnaty[®] vaccine formulation by BioNTech. In contrast to the actual vaccine, the here investigated samples do not contain mRNA and are not prepared in an acidic buffer (pH 4), but rather at neutral pH (pH 7) using a phosphate buffer. Furthermore, cryoprotective additives such as sucrose, which are included in Comirnaty[®], were not used.

The lipid mixtures for LNP preparation consisted of the following components:

- ALC-0315
- ALC-0159
- 1,2-Distearoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphatidylcholine (DSPC)
- Cholesterol

1.1 Replacement of ALC lipids

In contrast to the Comirnaty[®] formulation, in which the ionizable lipid ALC-0315 and the PEG-lipid ALC-0159 were used, these components were replaced in this work by **glyceryl trioctanoate** (GTO, Sigma Aldrich) and **DMG-PEG2000** (Avanti Polar Lipids), respectively. Cholesterol (Sigma Aldrich) and DSPC (Cayman Chemical Company) were used as additional components.

Since the molecular weights of these substitute molecules differ from those of the original ALC lipids, two different preparation strategies were applied:

1. **Mass-matched approach:** The same mass concentrations (mg/mL) as in [2] were used for the replacement lipids.
2. **Isomolar approach:** The number of molecules was kept constant. Therefore, the mass of each substitute lipid was recalculated from the molar amount of the original lipid, according to

$$m_{\text{new}} = \frac{m_{\text{orig}}}{M_{\text{orig}}} \cdot M_{\text{new}},$$

where m denotes the mass and M the molar mass of the lipid.

Original composition (reference study)

Component	M	C
ALC-0315 (BioNTech)	766.29	7.17
ALC-0159 (BioNTech)	2330	0.89
DSPC (Cayman Chemical)	790.16	1.56
Cholesterol (Sigma Aldrich)	386.65	3.10

Table 1: Original lipid. M in [g mol⁻¹], C in [mg mL⁻¹].

Modified composition (this work)

Replacement lipid	M	$m_{\text{Mass-Matched}}$	m_{Iso}
Glyceryl trioctanoate (Sigma Aldrich)	470.68	7.17	4.404
DMG-PEG2000 (Avanti Polar Lipids)	2509.2	0.89	0.958
DSPC (Cayman Chemical)	790.16	1.56	1.56
Cholesterol (Sigma Aldrich)	386.65	3.10	3.10

Table 2: Comparison of mass-matched and isomolar approaches. M in [g mol⁻¹], m in [mg mL⁻¹].

1.2 Sample preparation

For the preparation of the lipid dispersions, glyceryl trioctanoate (GTO) was the only component in liquid form, whereas DSPC, cholesterol, and DMG-PEG2000 were obtained as powders. Due to the viscous and oily nature of GTO, exact weighing was challenging. Therefore, the required amounts were transferred from the stock vial using an Eppendorf Research adjustable micropipette, which allowed for as precise dosing as possible, but inevitably led to small deviations from the target values.

In contrast, the powdered compounds were easier to handle. The components were weighed using a Sartorius Extend analytical balance (model ED224S-CW) with a protective glass draft shield, enabling precise mass determination down to 0.1 mg.

For ethanol ($\rho = 0.7899$ g/mL), which was needed in relatively larger amounts, weighing was performed on a Sartorius M-Power precision balance. The solvent was subsequently dispensed using a standard glass pipette with a rubber bulb.

For each formulation (mass-matched and isomolar), solutions with a final volume of 4 mL were prepared. Glyceryl trioctanoate and cholesterol were stored in the refrigerator at 6°C, whereas the other two components were kept in the freezer at -70°C until use.

Weighed amounts for sample preparation

The actual weighed amounts for the prepared samples are listed in the following tables. Small deviations from the target concentrations occurred, particularly for glyceryl trioctanoate, due to its viscous liquid nature.

Component	Mass-matched (S1)	Mass-matched (S2)	Isomolar (S3)
Glyceryl trioctanoate (GTO)	0.0360	0.03585	0.0204
DMG-PEG2000	0.00445	0.00446	0.00480
DSPC	0.0080	0.0080	0.0080
Cholesterol	0.0156	0.0158	0.0157
Ethanol	3.970	3.967	3.971

Table 3: Weighed amounts in [g] of lipids and solvent for the prepared samples: Two mass-matched formulations and one isomolar formulation.

1.2.1 Sodium phosphate buffer preparation

The sodium phosphate buffer was prepared to keep the dispersion medium at $\text{pH} \approx 7$. For this work, 50 mL of buffer solution was prepared in ultrapure D_2O (99.9% isotopic purity, Sigma Aldrich®). The required masses of the buffer components were weighed using a precision balance and then dissolved in the solvent.

An ultrasonic bath (EMAG Emmi-30HC from EMAG Technologies) was used to accelerate dissolution. Once the salts were fully dissolved, a clear and colorless buffer solution was obtained, which was directly used for the synthesis of the LNPs. After preparation, the pH of the buffer solution was verified using pH-Fix 6.0–7.7pH test strips from Macherey-Nagel. A small aliquot of the solution was applied to the strip, which developed a color within a few seconds. The resulting color was compared to the reference scale provided by the manufacturer to confirm that the pH was within the desired range.

Components	m [g]
Sodium chloride	6.00
Potassium chloride	0.015
Dibasic sodium phosphate dehydrate	1.08
Monobasic potassium phosphate	0.015

Table 4: Components for the Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS) buffer at pH 7, scaled for 1 L of D_2O .

1.2.2 Antisolvent precipitation with D_2O

For the preparation of lipid nanoparticles, the hydrophobic lipids were first dissolved in ethanol, yielding a homogeneous lipid solution. A total of 4 mL of this ethanol–lipid mixture was used for the precipitation process. To establish the required buffer-to-lipid ratio of 9:1, the lipid solution was combined with 4 mL of sodium phosphate buffer (prepared in D_2O) and further diluted with

an additional 8×4 mL of pure D_2O . This ratio was chosen because a much smaller lipid fraction relative to the buffer is essential to promote the formation of small and stable nanoparticles.

The solutions were merged using a pressurized injection system equipped with a pneumatic actuator (Festo, model DMM-12-20-P-A), which ensured a controlled and continuous flow of the lipid solution into the antisolvent phase and provided reproducible injection conditions. The process was carried out in standard 50 mL Falcon tubes, which served as reaction vessels that can withstand the applied pressure and allow for reproducible mixing conditions.

Directly after mixing, the dispersion turned milky, indicating the onset of nanoparticle formation. Over time, the suspension became more transparent as the lipid nanoparticles stabilized. To support rapid homogenization and equilibration, the Falcon tubes were placed in an ultrasonic bath. After approximately five minutes, the system reached equilibrium, resulting in a colloidal suspension of LNPs ready for further synthesis steps.

1.2.3 Centrifugation and Concentration of LNP Dispersions

After the synthesis of the lipid nanoparticles (LNPs) via antisolvent precipitation, the resulting dispersion contains not only the LNPs themselves but also a significant volume of solvent mixture—primarily deuterium oxide (D_2O), buffer salts, and residual ethanol from the injection phase.

To increase the concentration of the LNPs and remove excess solvent, the dispersion is subjected to a concentration step using a centrifugal vacuum evaporator (Eppendorf Concentrator plus, with Vacufuge plus system). The device operates in V-AQ mode, which is specifically optimized for aqueous samples, and is maintained at a temperature of 60°C . This configuration allows for the gentle evaporation of volatile components—most importantly, ethanol—without degrading the nanoparticle structure.

Under reduced pressure, the boiling points of ethanol and water (or D_2O) are significantly lowered. Ethanol, having the lowest boiling point among the solvents in the mixture, is the first to evaporate. Crucially, the LNPs do not degrade or evaporate, nor do the buffer salts. Thus, the concentration process was continued in repeated cycles of centrifugation and weighing, until the sample mass matched the predefined target corresponding to the desired final volume of 4 mL. Hence, the final sample is a significantly smaller volume of LNP dispersion that is free of ethanol, highly enriched in lipid nanoparticles, and still buffered in D_2O and salts.

This concentrated sample is then used in all subsequent structural characterization methods, such as Small-Angle Neutron Scattering (SANS), Small-Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS) and Photon Correlation Spectroscopy (PCS). It was transferred into 20 mm glass vials and sealed with ND20 aluminium tear-off caps (Carl Roth GmbH + Co. KG) using a manual crimping tool to ensure airtight closure and long-term sample stability.

2 Measurement

2.1 D22: SAXS/SANS at the Institut Laue-Langevin

At the Institut Laue-Langevin (ILL) in Grenoble, the high-performance D22 beamline is primarily used for small-angle neutron scattering (SANS). A unique feature of this instrument is the integration of an additional SAXS module, which allows simultaneous X-ray and neutron scattering measurements on the same sample. In our measurements, the sample cell was placed under a 45° angle with respect to the incoming beam. As a result, the effective sample thickness was increased by a factor of $\sqrt{2}$, resulting in an effective thickness of approximately 1.4 mm for a cell with a nominal thickness of 1 mm.

Parameter	SAXS	SANS
Sample–detector distance	1 m	12 m
Wavelength	1.54 Å	0.6 nm
Q-range	0.04 – 3.85 nm ⁻¹	0.04 – 3.85 nm ⁻¹
Collimation length	1.6 m	17.6 m

Table 5: Comparison of key experimental parameters for SAXS and SANS at the D22 beamline (ILL Grenoble).

2.2 Complementarity of SAXS and SANS

Although SAXS and SANS both covered the same Q -ranges at the D22 setup, their contrast mechanisms are fundamentally different. X-rays interact with the electron density of the sample, making them especially sensitive to regions with higher electron density such as lipid headgroups or sterol components. This typically provides detailed information on smaller structural features, such as shell thicknesses of a few nanometers. Neutrons, by contrast, probe nuclear scattering length densities and allow for isotopic contrast variation (e.g. using D₂O). As a result, SANS is well suited to highlight larger structural domains, hydration layers, or the distribution of different lipid species in the nanoparticle core.

For LNPs, SAXS therefore emphasizes the fine structure of the shells, while SANS provides complementary insights into the overall particle organization, solvent penetration, and contrast between different molecular components. In combination, both techniques yield a comprehensive structural picture across size scales from 1 nm up to several hundred nanometers.

2.3 Correction for Sample Holder and Background Noise

In small-angle scattering, the measured intensity always contains contributions not only from the sample itself but also from the sample holder and from background noise. Therefore, additional measurements are required. In the case of SANS: (i) with the sample and holder (I_S), (ii) with the empty holder (I_E), and (iii) with a cadmium absorber (I_{Cd}), which blocks the direct neutron beam and thus allows to measure only the background intensity. The corrected intensity is obtained using the data reduction formula:

$$I_{\text{corr}} = \frac{1}{T_S T_E} [I_S - I_{Cd}] - \frac{1}{T_E} [I_E - I_{Cd}], \tag{1}$$

where "S" stands for sample and "E" for empty. T_S and T_E denote the transmissions of the sample and the empty holder, respectively. The first term accounts for the measured sample plus holder intensity

normalized by its transmission and corrected for the background. The second term subtracts the appropriately scaled empty holder intensity and is also background-corrected.

For obtaining only the scattering of the LNPs the buffer scattering, measured separately under identical conditions, was subtracted from I_{corr} to isolate the scattering originating from the nanoparticles themselves.

At this stage, the resulting I_{corr} represents detector counts. An absolute calibration is required and will be discussed in the following section.

2.4 Calibration

Accurate small-angle scattering requires two independent calibrations: (i) a Q -scale calibration that maps detector pixels to the magnitude of the scattering vector Q , and (ii) an intensity calibration that converts counts to absolute units.

2.4.1 Q -scale calibration

For the SANS measurements performed in this work, no additional Q -scale calibration was required, since the instrument geometry (sample-to-detector distance and beam center) was well known and kept constant.

For the SAXS measurements, however, a Q -scale calibration was necessary. For this purpose, silver behenate (AgBe) was measured as a calibration standard. AgBe exhibits well-defined Bragg peaks at known Q -values, with the first maximum appearing at $Q_1 \approx 0.1076 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$. By recording the diffraction pattern of AgBe under the same conditions as the sample, the beam center and the ring radii on the detector can be determined. Matching the observed ring radii with the known Q -values allows one to refine the sample-to-detector distance and thereby obtain an accurate Q -scale, ensuring that the pixel positions are correctly converted into scattering vectors.

2.4.2 Intensity calibration

The raw scattering intensities recorded by the detector are not given in absolute physical units, but rather in arbitrary units such as detector counts. This means that the measured intensity cannot be directly interpreted as a differential scattering cross-section. In order to compare different measurements and to obtain results in physical units (e.g. cm^{-1} or barn), the intensity has to be calibrated with respect to a well-characterized reference standard.

Hence, the principle of intensity calibration is to measure a standard material with a known and reproducible scattering cross-section under the same conditions as the sample. The ratio of the measured intensity of the sample to that of the standard can then be used to determine a scaling factor, which converts the detector counts into absolute units.

2.4.3 SANS calibration

In Grenoble, the SANS data was collected without an extra calibration, whereas the SAXS measurements were calibrated using glassy carbon. The reason for this choice is that glassy carbon is amorphous, meaning it does not exhibit sharp Bragg peaks, but instead produces a smooth and reproducible scattering pattern. Furthermore, its electron density is very well defined and stable over time, which makes it an ideal reference for intensity calibration.

Absolute scattering intensities were obtained using the software GRASP. For this procedure, the relevant experimental parameters such as sample thickness and transmission were included, ensuring that absorption and multiple scattering were properly accounted for. In addition, the detector

response was corrected for efficiency, based on prior flatfield water measurements, and further normalized for relative efficiency variations between the different detector panels. A correction for detector parallax was also applied, compensating for the geometrical deviation of the flat detector from the ideal spherical geometry assumed in the data reduction.

Finally, the 2D detector pattern $I(Q_x, Q_y)$ was reduced to the 1D curve $I(|\vec{Q}|)$ by azimuthal averaging over concentric annuli about the beam center (assuming isotropic scattering).

2.5 Multiple Scattering Correction

Multiple scattering refers to neutrons being scattered more than once inside the sample before detection, which distorts the measured intensity. To account for this effect, the MuScatt software package was used [7]. The program requires basic experimental parameters such as sample thickness and transmission, and performs a correction based on theoretical models as described in the manual.

2.6 Photon Correlation Spectroscopy

Photon Correlation Spectroscopy (PCS) is a technique used to determine particle sizes. The method relies on the Brownian motion of particles: Smaller particles diffuse more rapidly than larger ones, which results in faster fluctuations of the scattered light intensity and thus a faster decay of the correlation function. Sizes can go from the micrometer down to the lower nanometer scale [1]. The particle size is related to the diffusion coefficient via the Stokes–Einstein equation,

$$D = \frac{k_B T}{6\pi\eta R_h}, \quad (2)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T the temperature, η the solvent viscosity, and R_h the hydrodynamic radius.

For polydisperse samples, the field autocorrelation function is expressed as

$$g^{(1)}(\tau) = \int_0^\infty G(\Gamma) e^{-\Gamma\tau} d\Gamma, \quad (3)$$

with $G(\Gamma)$ denoting the distribution of decay rates $\Gamma = Dq^2$, where q is the scattering vector. Recovering $G(\Gamma)$, and thus the particle size distribution, from $g^{(1)}(\tau)$ constitutes an ill-posed inversion problem.

Photon correlation measurements were carried out using a Litesizer DLS 500 instrument from Anton Paar GmbH. For the measurements, disposable cuvettes with four optical windows (BRAND GmbH und CO KG, UV-transparent, $12.5 \times 12.5 \times 45$ mm) were used. Each cuvette was filled with ultrapure D₂O up to a level between 9 mm and 15 mm as indicated on the instrument's cuvette holder. Subsequently, three droplets of the LNP dispersion were added to the cuvette using a Omnifix[®] syringe (B. Braun Melsungen AG).

Prior to each run, the suspension was equilibrated to a constant temperature of 25°C. The scattered light was recorded at a detection angle of 90°, while the system was illuminated with a laser source operating at a wavelength of $\lambda = 658$ nm. In the instrument software, the sample material was set to "phospholipids" and the solvent to "water". From these conditions, the corresponding autocorrelation function was obtained. Software then calculated the corresponding particle size distributions. For each sample, ten repeated measurements were made.

3 Theory

3.1 Particle Size Distributions

In many physical systems, additive random processes can be modeled by a normal distribution. In contrast, when growth or variation results from multiplicative processes, the logarithm of the variable becomes normally distributed. Consequently, particle size distributions (PSDs) of colloidal systems are commonly modeled by a log-normal distribution.

In SASfit, the log-normal distribution is implemented in the following form [3]:

$$\text{LogNorm}(X, \mu, \sigma, p) = \frac{N}{c_{\text{LN}} X^p} \exp\left(-\frac{(\ln(X/\mu))^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), \quad (4)$$

with the normalization factor

$$c_{\text{LN}} = \sqrt{2\pi} \sigma \mu^{1-p} \exp\left(\frac{(1-p)^2 \sigma^2}{2}\right). \quad (5)$$

Here, μ is the location parameter (related to the most probable size), σ characterizes the distribution width, and p is a shape parameter. N denotes the particle number density, given in nm^{-3} .

The quantity X represents the distributed variable. Hence, in the context of small-angle scattering models for spherical particles, X often corresponds to the particle radius R .

3.2 Form factor for a core-shell model

In small-angle scattering, the form factor $F(\mathbf{Q})$ of a particle is defined as the Fourier transform of the excess scattering length density $\rho(\mathbf{r})$ relative to the solvent [8, p. 91]:

$$F(\mathbf{Q}) = \int_V \rho(\mathbf{r}) e^{i\mathbf{Q}\cdot\mathbf{r}} d^3r. \quad (6)$$

where $Q = |\mathbf{Q}|$ is the magnitude of the scattering vector and R is the outer particle radius. The factor $\sin(Qr)/(Qr)$ arises from the angular average over orientations and is directly related to the spherical Bessel function of order one.

Evaluating this integral for a region of constant contrast $\Delta\eta$ within a sphere of radius R yields the expression

$$K(Q, R, \Delta\eta) = \frac{4}{3}\pi R^3 \Delta\eta \frac{3[\sin(QR) - QR \cos(QR)]}{(QR)^3}, \quad (7)$$

which is the building block for core-shell form factors in SASfit [3, Eq. 3.1b].

If the particle consists of a spherical core surrounded by several concentric shells, each region is characterized by a distinct scattering length density (SLD) η_i and radius R_i . In this case, the total form factor can be expressed as a sum over the individual spherical contributions, each weighted by the contrast relative to its next surrounding region. The general expression reads

$$F(Q) = \sum_{i=0}^N (\eta_i - \eta_{i+1}) V(R_i) f(QR_i), \quad (8)$$

where

$$V(R_i) = \frac{4}{3}\pi R_i^3, \quad f(QR_i) = \frac{3[\sin(QR_i) - QR_i \cos(QR_i)]}{(QR_i)^3}. \quad (9)$$

3.2.1 Form factor for a bilayered vesicle

Analogous to the core-shell model, the form factor of a bilayered vesicle can be written as a sum of contributions from the individual concentric regions, each weighted by its SLD contrast relative to the surrounding region. Following the SASfit manual [3], the form factor reads

$$F_{\text{BLV}}(Q) = K(Q, R_c, \eta_{\text{sol}} - \eta_h) + K(Q, R_c + t_h, \eta_h - \eta_t) + K(Q, R_c + t_h + t_t, \eta_t - \eta_h) + K(Q, R_c + 2t_h + t_t, \eta_h - \eta_{\text{sol}}), \quad (10)$$

where $K(Q, R, \Delta\eta)$ is given by

$$K(Q, R, \Delta\eta) = \frac{4}{3}\pi R^3 \Delta\eta \frac{3[\sin(QR) - QR \cos(QR)]}{(QR)^3}. \quad (11)$$

Input Parameters:

- R_c : Radius of the solvent-filled core.
- t_h : Thickness of the bilayer headgroup region.
- t_t : Thickness of the bilayer tail region.
- η_{sol} : SLD of the solvent.
- η_h : SLD of the bilayer headgroup region.
- η_t : SLD of the bilayer tail region.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the bilayered vesicle model, showing the solvent core radius R_c , the headgroup and tailgroup thicknesses t_h and t_t , and the corresponding scattering length densities $\eta_{\text{sol}}, \eta_h, \eta_t$. Figure adapted from the SASfit manual [3], p. 65.

3.3 Intensity

For a dilute isotropic dispersion of spherical particles, the measured small-angle scattering intensity is proportional to the absolute value squared of the orientationally averaged single-particle form factor. In the case of polydispersity with a radius distribution $p(R)$, the intensity becomes

$$I(Q) = \int p(R) |F(Q, R)|^2 dR, \quad (12)$$

where $F(Q, R)$ denotes the form factor amplitude of a sphere with radius R [6].

The experimental data from polydisperse samples is typically much smoother or even washed out in comparison to the sharp peaks visible for monodisperse samples.

Figure 2: Monodisperse sphere form factor intensity $I(Q)$ for two radii ($R = 10$ nm and $R = 20$ nm). The pronounced oscillations and deep minima are characteristic of a monodisperse sphere. In experimental data these oscillations are smoothed out by a continuous size distribution. Figure adapted from the SASfit User's Guide [3].

3.4 SASfit

SASfit [3] is a software used for fitting small-angle scattering data. It provides a framework to connect the theoretical description of particle size distributions and form factors with the experimentally measured scattering intensity $I(Q)$. In practice, SASfit allows the user to define particle size distributions (e.g. log-normal distributions), assign appropriate form factors and, if needed, include structure factors in order to model interparticle interactions. Based on these inputs, the program calculates the resulting scattering curve $I(Q)$ and enables direct comparison with experimental data by means of fitting routines.

In this way, SASfit can be used to refine particle and interaction parameters, visualize theoretical scattering models, and quantitatively compare them with the measured curves.

Figure 3: Setup of the SASfit fitting model. In this example, a log-normal particle size distribution (dark blue) is combined with a form factor corresponding to a sphere with three shells (light blue). The orange box shows the parameters of the log-normal distribution. The green box contains the geometrical parameters of the three-shell sphere. The red box shows the SLDs for the core and the three shells. The solvent SLD is not visible in the screenshot, as it appears further down in the parameter list.

3.5 Gaussian size distribution

In addition to log-normal size distributions, Gaussian (or normal) distributions were also evaluated during the fitting process. Figure 4 illustrates the parameter setup for a Gaussian distribution within SASfit. Here, the normalization constant N , the width parameter σ , and the mean value x_0 are defined as input variables, and the resulting Gaussian distribution is then combined with the chosen form factor (e.g. a sphere with three shells) in order to model the scattering intensity $I(Q)$.

Figure 4: Parameter menu for a Gaussian size distribution in SASfit.

The Gaussian distribution implemented in SASfit is defined as [3]:

$$\text{Gauss}(R, N, \sigma, R_0) = \frac{N}{c_{\text{Gauss}}} \exp\left[-\frac{(R - R_0)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right], \quad (13)$$

$$c_{\text{Gauss}} = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}} \sigma \left(1 + \text{erf}\left(\frac{R_0}{\sqrt{2}\sigma}\right)\right), \quad (14)$$

where the normalization constant c_{Gauss} is chosen such that

$$\int_0^{\infty} \text{Gauss}(R, \sigma, R_0) dR = N. \quad (15)$$

Here R_0 denotes the mean (center) of the distribution, σ the standard deviation (width), and N a scaling factor controlling the amplitude of the distribution. The function $\text{erf}(x)$ denotes the error function, which is defined as

$$\text{erf}(x) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x e^{-t^2} dt.$$

It arises naturally in Gaussian integrals and is used here to guarantee proper normalization of the truncated distribution (restricted to $R > 0$).

3.6 Sticky hard sphere structure factor

In addition to form factors, the data analysis also required the use of a structure factor that accounts for interparticle correlations. A commonly used model is the sticky hard sphere structure factor, which is based on Baxter’s model of adhesive hard spheres [3]. The idea of this model is that particles are treated as hard spheres that can experience a short-range attractive interaction, hence the name “sticky”.

In SASfit, the sticky hard sphere structure factor is implemented through three parameters: the hard sphere radius R_{HS} , the volume fraction f_p , and the stickiness parameter τ which quantifies the adhesive strength. The corresponding expression is written as

$$S_{\text{sHS}}(q, R_{\text{HS}}, f_p, \tau) = \frac{1}{1 - C(q)}, \quad (16)$$

where $C(q)$ is a function of q , R_{HS} , f_p , and τ . The explicit form of $C(q)$ is relatively complex, involving combinations of trigonometric terms and powers of qR_{HS} and can be looked up in the SASfit manual.

Figure 5: Parameter menu for the sticky hard sphere structure factor in SASfit.

3.7 Fit-quality: The (weighted) R-factor

In order to evaluate the quality of a fit, SASfit provides additional statistical indicators, among them the R -factor and the weighted R -factor R_w [3]. These quantities serve as indicators of how well the calculated scattering curve agrees with the measured data. However, it must be emphasized that a low R -factor does not necessarily imply that the chosen physical model is accurate, but only that the fit reproduces the measured curve with high precision.

The R -factor is defined as

$$R = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N |I_{\text{exp}}(Q_i) - I_{\text{th}}(Q_i)|}{\sum_{i=1}^N I_{\text{exp}}(Q_i)}, \quad (17)$$

where $I_{\text{exp}}(Q_i)$ and q_i denote the coordinates of measurement point i and $I_{\text{th}}(Q_i)$ the corresponding theoretical value from the fit.

The weighted R -factor is defined as

$$R_w = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{I_{\text{exp}}(Q_i) - I_{\text{th}}(Q_i)}{\Delta I(Q_i)} \right)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{I_{\text{exp}}(Q_i)}{\Delta I(Q_i)} \right)^2}}, \quad (18)$$

where $\Delta I(Q_i)$ denotes the experimental uncertainty (standard deviation) of the intensity at Q_i . In practice, the following guidelines can be used for interpretation:

- $R, R_w < 0.05$: fit considered good,
- $R, R_w < 0.1$: fit results are generally believable,

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Starting model

Figure 6: Schematic representation of the core-shell structure of lipid nanoparticles according to Unruh et al.[9]. The model features a homogeneous core of cholesterol and ALC-0315 (and mRNA in the case of Comirnaty[®]), surrounded by concentric stabilizing shells.

The starting point for the mesoscopic model was chosen in accordance with the model proposed by Unruh et al.[9]. The LNPs are described as a core-shell system. However, it is assumed that both ALCs are replaced by their aforementioned substitutes. The innermost region, referred to as the LNP core, has a radius of approximately 21 nm and consists primarily of cholesterol and glyceryl trioctanoate. Directly surrounding the core is the first shell (t_1), which is considered part of the core structure itself. The second shell ($t_2 \approx 2.4$ nm) represents the stabilizing layer, composed mainly of DSPC, cholesterol. The outermost shell ($t_3 \approx 4$ nm) contains the polyethylene glycol (PEG) chains of DMG-PEG2000 that extend into the surrounding solvent. In this project, the dispersion medium is deuterium oxide (D_2O), which provides the solvent contrast for neutron scattering experiments. This layered structure with ingredient-dependent scattering length densities provides the basis for describing the small-angle scattering patterns of LNPs. Since the X-ray measurements showed significantly lower data quality and limited contrast. Hence, only the neutron scattering results were considered for the subsequent analysis.

Name of substance	Chemical formula	Mass density (g/mL)	X-ray SLD (10^{10} cm^{-2})	Neutron SLD (10^{10} cm^{-2})
DSPC ^a	$\text{C}_{44}\text{H}_{88}\text{NO}_8\text{P}$	1.0	9.441	0.184
Cholesterol ^b	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}$	0.956	9.678	0.210
DMG-PEG2000 ^a	$\text{C}_{122}\text{H}_{242}\text{O}_{50}$	1.0	9.326	0.470
Glyceryl trioctanoate ^a	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_6$	0.434	9.344	0.333
ALC-0315 ^b	$\text{C}_{48}\text{H}_{95}\text{NO}_5$	0.889	8.481	0.0152
ALC-0159 ^a	$\text{C}_{121}\text{H}_{243}\text{NO}_{47}$	1.0	9.326	0.434
D_2O + salts ^b	D_2O + salts	1.0023	9.434	6.355

^a Values calculated using the SLD calculator in SASfit.

^b Values taken from [9].

Table 6: Mass densities and calculated scattering length densities for the compounds used in the present LNP model. Values are given at $T = 25^\circ\text{C}$.

4.2 Particle size distribution

For the modeling of the scattering data, the approach suggested by Unruh et al. [9] was taken as a guideline. In this framework, the particle size distribution is represented as the sum of five separate components. The first four components are described by log-normal distributions, while the fifth one follows a Gaussian distribution. In practice, only the first two fractions contribute significantly to the overall scattering signal. Fractions three to five correspond to larger particles, which mainly affect the intensity at very small q -values. Their influence on the fitted scattering curves is negligible, but they are nevertheless included to ensure consistency with the complementary PCS data. The resulting function is therefore expressed as

$$F(Q) = \sum_{i=1}^5 f_i(Q), \quad (19)$$

where each $f_i(Q)$ denotes the contribution of the respective fraction.

4.3 PCS results

In the following, the PCS results are discussed. As an example, the analysis of Sample 1 is shown in detail. The other two samples yielded analogous results, with no significant deviations in the characteristic features, so that Sample 1 can be taken as representative.

The intensity autocorrelation functions $g_2(\tau)$ of ten consecutive PCS measurements of Sample 1 are shown in Figure 7. The curves nearly overlap; the characteristic delay time (knee of the curve) varies only slightly across runs. Nevertheless, when transforming to particle-size distributions, even such small differences in $g_2(\tau)$ can map onto noticeably different PSDs.

The volume-weighted PSD (Figure 8) exhibits a pronounced first (“sharp”) peak at 30 nm diameter. The number-weighted PSD (Figure 9) shows the corresponding peak at slightly smaller diameters, consistent with the different weighting. A broader, low-amplitude feature appears at larger sizes and becomes visible when zooming in (Figure 10), roughly in the 250 – 350 nm range.

The PCS measurements were mainly intended to provide a rough first estimate of the particle size distribution and to verify that the results are broadly consistent with the more detailed PSD models developed in the following sections.

Figure 7: Autocorrelation functions $g_2(\tau)$ for ten PCS runs of Sample 1.

Figure 8: Volume-weighted PSD (v PSD) for ten PCS measurements of Sample 1. A sharp peak near 30 nm is consistently observed.

Figure 9: Number-weighted PSD (n PSD) for the same ten measurements. Peak positions shift slightly compared to v PSD, as expected from the weighting.

Figure 10: Zoomed-in PSD views for Sample 1 highlighting (left) the first sharp peak around 30 nm and (right) a broad high-diameter feature around 250–350 nm.

4.4 Calculation of the scattering length densities

In order to determine the scattering length densities (SLDs) of the individual layers in the core-shell model, weighted averages of the pure component SLDs were calculated. For each layer, the SLD was obtained as the sum of the weight fraction w_i of each component multiplied by its respective SLD,

$$\text{SLD}_{\text{mix}} = \sum_i w_i \text{SLD}_i. \quad (20)$$

The weight fractions were taken from the values reported by Unruh *et al.* for drug-free dispersions [9], with the substitution of the original ionizable lipids by alternative compounds in the present work. Specifically, the composition of the layers was defined as follows:

- **Core:** 94 w% glyceryl trioctanoate, 6 w% cholesterol (instead of ALC-0315 + cholesterol).
- **Shell 1 (t_1):** Same as core
- **Shell 2 ($t_2 \approx 2.4$ nm):** 58.5 w% cholesterol, 38 w% DSPC, and 3.5 w% DMG-PEG2000 (instead of ALC-0159).
- **Shell 3 ($t_3 \approx 4$ nm):** dominated by PEG chains highly swollen with solvent; therefore, the SLD of the solvent ($\text{D}_2\text{O} + \text{salts}$) was assumed.

Using this approach, the effective SLD values for each layer were calculated and implemented in SASfit. Table 7 lists the resulting SLDs as used in the fits.

Table 7: Effective SLDs of the layers used in the SASfit core-shell model for drug-free LNP dispersions. Values are given [10^{10} cm^{-2}].

Layer	Neutron SLD	X-ray SLD
Core (glyceryl trioctanoate + cholesterol)	0.325641	5.03128
Shell 1 (core contribution)	0.325641	5.03128
Shell 2 (cholesterol + DSPC + DMG-PEG2000)	0.208165	3.57625
Shell 3 (PEG + solvent)	6.3553	9.4186

4.5 Different Models for the LNPs

In the experimental data it was observed that at higher q -values, roughly beginning at $0.3\text{--}0.4 \text{ nm}^{-1}$, the decay of the intensity is slightly less steep than in the measurements reported by Unruh [9] and Gallo [2]. Hence, some additions to the starting model were needed. This motivated the development of two different approaches, resulting in two models that are presented in the following sections in order to account for the observed intensity behavior.

4.6 Model 1: Mixture of Liposomes and LNPs

4.6.1 Core-shell model with three shells

In order to fit the data, the contrast between adjacent shells was chosen to be maximal, enhancing the scattered intensity at higher Q . The resulting model consists of a hydrophobic core containing glyceril and cholesterol, followed by an inner aqueous layer, a middle bilayer containing cholesterol and DSPC, and finally an outer shell that can again be approximated by water. This layered structure is sketched in Fig. 11.

Figure 11: Schematic representation of the fitted three-shell core model with alternating high-contrast layers (core, water, lipid-rich shell, water).

This bilayered vesicle model was the first approach that provided a reasonable fit and reproduced the experimentally observed increase in intensity at higher Q values.

However, such a model is physically unreasonable: A repeated solvent-bilayer-solvent layering has never been observed for these systems and would be highly unrealistic from a structural point of view.

Nevertheless, this model served as an important motivation for developing the next model, which is more physically plausible and consistent with the expected particle composition.

Figure 12: Scattering data of Sample 3. The quality of the fit is characterized by an R -factor of 0.0894 and a weighted R_w of 0.0535.

4.6.2 Mixture of LNPs and liposomes

The high-contrast model led to the assumption of a mixed system, consisting of lipid nanoparticles and a population of lipid vesicles (liposomes) containing a hydrated aqueous core. Their formation could be due to an excess of stabilizing components. Thus, additional liposomes form, which consist mainly of DSPC, cholesterol, and heavy-water. The particle shell is described as a lipid bilayer composed mainly of DSPC, and cholesterol. Hydrophilic headgroups face the aqueous phases (inside and outside), while hydrophobic tails meet in the bilayer midplane. The liposome core is assumed to be filled with water.

Figure 13: Schematic representation of a liposome structure, showing the hydrophilic aqueous core, the phospholipid bilayer with hydrophobic tails, and cholesterol molecules intercalated within the membrane. Figure adapted from Nsairat et al. [5].

4.6.3 Physical plausibility

While vesicles have not been reported for LNP systems in the findings of Unruh [9] and Gallo [2], the present model is not inconsistent: While the model does require a relatively large fraction of cholesterol and DSPC to be located within the bilayer, the amount of material required to form such a bilayered population is within the range provided by the sample composition.

For a plausibility check of the vesicle fraction, it is now estimated how much DSPC volume is required to form the vesicle bilayers compared to the DSPC present in the LNP shells. For the vesicles a tail thickness of $t_{t,\text{ves}} = 3.48$ nm was assumed, while the headgroup thickness was set to zero ($t_{h,\text{ves}} = 0$) because the headgroups do not contribute to the neutron contrast. For the LNPs a tail thickness of $t_{t,\text{lnp}} = 2.4$ nm and a core radius of $R_{\text{lnp}} = 17$ nm were used. The inner vesicle radius was taken from the fit as $R_{\text{ves}} = 38.6$ nm, as well as the relative number of particles, with $\frac{N_{\text{ves}}}{N_{\text{lnp}}} = \frac{2}{14}$.

The ratio of total DSPC volume used in vesicles relative to LNPs can thus be expressed as

$$\mathcal{R} = \frac{N_{\text{ves}} \cdot \frac{4\pi}{3} [(R_{\text{ves}} + t_{t,\text{ves}})^3 - R_{\text{ves}}^3]}{N_{\text{lnp}} \cdot \frac{4\pi}{3} [(R_{\text{lnp}} + t_{t,\text{lnp}})^3 - R_{\text{lnp}}^3]} = \frac{2}{14} \frac{(38.6 \text{ nm} + 3.48 \text{ nm})^3 - (38.6 \text{ nm})^3}{(17 \text{ nm} + 2.4 \text{ nm})^3 - (17 \text{ nm})^3} \approx \mathbf{1.02}.$$

Hence, the vesicle fraction would require about 102% of the DSPC volume present in the LNP fraction, i.e. roughly the same order of magnitude. This indicates that, from a compositional point of view, the presence of vesicles at the fitted population ratio is physically plausible.

To verify whether a significant number of vesicles is indeed present in the sample, complementary techniques such as cryogenic transmission electron microscopy (cryo-TEM) could be employed. Direct imaging would allow for an independent estimation of the vesicle population and thus provide an experimental validation of the model.

Figure 14: Fit to the scattering data of sample 3, corrected for multiple scattering. The fit quality is characterized by an R -factor of 0.1090 and a weighted R_w of 0.066.

4.7 Model 2: Crystalline cholesterol in the core

In order to explain the observed increase in intensity at higher Q -values, it was hypothesized that cholesterol may form a crystalline phase within the core of the LNPs. In this scenario, the core would consist of a mixture of glyceryl trioctanoate and cholesterol, where the cholesterol crystallizes and thereby introduces an additional structural feature that gives rise to the observed scattering contribution.

Experimental data shows that cholesterol exhibits only a limited solubility in triglyceride matrices at room temperature. In a classical study on the saturation solubility of cholesterol in pure triglycerides at 37°C, the maximum solubility in glyceryl trioctanoate was found to be approximately 4.4 wt% [4].

A simple experimental test of cholesterol solubility in glyceryl trioctanoate was performed. Based on the LNP formulation, the two lipids were mixed in a mass ratio of approximately 7:3 (glyceryl trioctanoate to cholesterol), with a total amount of 4 mg glyceryl trioctanoate. At room temperature, the mixture was not miscible and remained biphasic. Upon strong heating with a heat gun, however, the sample gradually turned into a clear homogeneous solution (see Fig. 15).

Figure 15: Mixture of glyceryl trioctanoate and cholesterol (7:3) after heating: Homogeneous clear solution.

When the heated solution was cooled back to room temperature, the mixture underwent phase separation again. The sample solidified into a waxy or gel-like mass, showing clear evidence of precipitation (Fig. 16). Closer inspection suggested that crystalline cholesterol had precipitated, embedded within the surrounding oil phase. This impression was supported by the observation that droplets of oil could be blotted off from the surface, whereas the solid residue appeared more crystalline and rigid.

Figure 16: Same mixture after cooling: Waxy, crystalline precipitate of cholesterol embedded in oil phase.

4.7.1 Fit attempt with crystalline inclusions in the core

To accommodate the hypothesized crystalline cholesterol inside the LNP core, an additional particle fraction was introduced in the fit: Monodisperse spheres with a lognormal size distribution intended to represent many small crystallites embedded in the core. A comparatively high SLD of $\eta = 2 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ was required for this fraction to generate sufficient contrast. Because the center-to-center distances of these small spheres inside the core become small, interparticle correlations were modeled with a sticky hard-sphere structure factor $S(Q)$.

From geometry, the maximal number of spherical inclusions that can fill the core (ignoring packing) scales as

$$N_{\max} \simeq \frac{V_{\text{core}}}{V_{\text{incl}}} = \frac{\frac{4}{3}\pi R_c^3}{\frac{4}{3}\pi r_{\text{incl}}^3} = \left(\frac{R_c}{r_{\text{incl}}}\right)^3, \quad (21)$$

and with a volume fraction ϕ of inclusions inside the core,

$$N_{\text{incl}} \simeq \phi N_{\max} = \phi \left(\frac{R_c}{r_{\text{incl}}}\right)^3. \quad (22)$$

For the fitted core radius $R_c \approx 17$ nm and the lower bound of the inclusion radii $r_{\text{incl}} \approx 3.2$ nm this yields $N_{\text{max}} \approx (\frac{17}{3.2})^3 \approx 1.50 \times 10^2$. With the (small) structure-factor volume fractions used in the fits ($\phi = 0.01$) one obtains $N_{\text{incl}} \approx 1.5$.

However, the fitted exponent N had to be chosen significantly larger than that in order to fit the data. Also the choices for η and ϕ that had to be made to fit the data, are physically unrealistic, considering that the SLD difference between cholesterol and the oil is one order of magnitude smaller than the assumed SLD in the fit, and the volume fraction should be significantly higher when a large number of particles is assumed to be present in the core. Hence, it can be concluded that the model does not provide a physically reasonable description of the data. Moreover, trying to include this model into Model 1 also did not provide any improvement to the fit in Model 1.

Figure 17: Scattering data of sample 3. The fit reproduces the data very well, with an R -factor of 0.0486 and a weighted R_w of 0.0371.

Figure 18: Scattering data of sample 1. The fit reproduces the data very well, with an R -factor of 0.0397 and a weighted R_w of 0.0184.

5 Conclusion

The aim of this research project was to formulate LNPs in which the ionizable lipid ALC-0315 and the PEG-lipid ALC-0159 were replaced by glyceryl trioctanoate and DMG-PEG2000, respectively. These particles were analyzed using complementary techniques, namely photon correlation spectroscopy and combined SAXS/SANS experiments.

Two structural models were developed in order to interpret the scattering data. The initial model, based on the established approach from Unruh et al. [9], could not fully account for the strong high- Q intensity observed in SANS measurements. Therefore, two modifications were introduced: (i) a model including an additional population of liposomes, and (ii) a model assuming the presence of crystalline cholesterol in the LNP core. The results indicate that the model with crystalline cholesterol does not provide a reasonable description of the data. On the other hand, the model including liposomes fit to the data and the assumptions made in the fitting procedure appear physically plausible. Nevertheless, it is also conceivable that both effects coexist, i.e. a crystalline core in the LNPs, as well as the presence of liposomes.

Future investigations, for example using cryo-TEM, will be necessary to resolve these ambiguities and to determine whether the proposed models accurately describe the internal organization of the LNPs or whether alternative structural models may be more appropriate.

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Data Availability

Measurement data, processed datasets, and fitting results of this research project are openly available under the DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17165639>.

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